

Potentiometric Studies on Chelation of Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) with some 5-Aryl-1-phenyl-4-pentene-1,3-diones

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Literature is extensive on the chemistry and applications of metal complexes of 1,3-diketones in which the carbonyl groups are attached to alkyl/aryl groups¹. However, reports are scanty on the coordination behaviour of dicarbonyl function attached directly to alkenyl (-CH=CH-) groups. Such 'unsaturated' 1,3-dicarbonyl moieties are the basic structural units present in curcuminoids, the active constituent of *Curcuma longa*, a traditional Indian medicinal plant, and several other biologically important plant products². As a part of our investigations on such medicinally important compounds, here we report the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of a series of 5-aryl-1-phenyl-4-pentene-1,3-diones (**1a-e**) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane medium. The method of study involved is the pH-metric titration technique as adapted by Irving and Rossotti³.

- 1a**; R₁ = H, R₂ = H
1b; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = H
1c; R₁ = OH, R₂ = H
1d; R₁ = OH, R₂ = OCH₃
1e; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = OCH₃

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand formation number (\bar{n}_A) were calculated at various pH values from the titration curves. The pK values were calculated by half-integral and mid-point calculation methods³ from the pH vs \bar{n}_A plots. The mean values are presented in Table 1. The pK_(enolic) values of these compounds are significantly higher than the corresponding values reported for saturated analogues such as acetylacetone and benzoylacetone^{4,5}. This indicates that extended conjugation increases the stability of the enolic form. The pK_(enolic) values are found to increase from **1a** through **1e** (Table 1) and this can be attributed to the increasing electron-releasing tendencies of the substituents in the aryl ring.

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Compd. no.	pK _(enolic)	pK _(phenolic)
1a	11.31	-
1b	12.08	-
1c	12.45	10.82
1d	13.12	10.85
1e	13.38	-

In the case of metal-ligand formation studies, the \bar{n} (the average metal-ligand formation number) and pL values were calculated from the titration curves³. The formation curves of metal complexes were obtained by plotting pL against \bar{n} . The \bar{n} values extend upto 2.0, indicating the formation of [ML] and [ML₂] complexes. The overall stability constants calculated are presented in Table 2. It follows that the stability of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} agrees with the Irving-Williams natural order. The log k_n values follow an increasing trend and it can also be correlated with the effect of electron-releasing groups in the ligand molecule. The order of formation constants, log $k_1 > \log k_2$ indicates a decrease in bond strength with the successive attachment of ligand molecules, and the observed small differences between the two values suggest the *trans*-configuration of the chelates.

TABLE 2-METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Metal(II) ion	Stability constant	Ligands				
		1a	1b	1c	1d	1e
Cu	log k_1	11.0	11.62	12.10	12.80	12.85
	log k_2	9.8	10.40	10.50	11.22	11.20
	log β	20.8	22.02	22.60	24.02	24.05
Ni	log k_1	8.01	8.35	8.75	8.90	9.00
	log k_2	7.33	7.65	7.85	8.00	8.10
	log β	15.43	16.00	16.60	16.90	17.10
Co	log k_1	7.40	7.73	8.10	8.30	8.40
	log k_2	6.82	7.00	7.30	7.40	7.62
	log β	14.22	14.73	15.40	15.70	16.02

The theoretical formation curves calculated from measured values of log k and pL coincides with the experimental points. The plots of log k_n vs pK gave satisfactory linear relationship suggesting that the partial molar free energy values of metal-ligand and proton-ligand complexes exactly compensate each other⁵.

The observed metal-ligand stability constants of these compounds far exceed from those reported for acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, etc.^{4,5}. This indicates that the attachment of an alkenyl group adjacent to the dicarbonyl function considerably enhances the chelating ability of the 1,3-diketonyl function.

Experimental

Compounds **la-e** were obtained from the condensation of benzoylacetone with aromatic aldehydes (benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and veratraldehyde) by the following general procedure. A solution of the aromatic aldehyde (0.0025 mol) in dry ethyl acetate (5 ml) and tri(*s*-butyl)borate (0.01 mol) were added to a stirred mixture of benzoylacetone (0.0075 mol), dry ethyl acetate (2 ml) and boric oxide (0.005 mol). After stirring the mixture for ~1 h, *n*-butylamine (0.05 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring during 30 min, the stirring was continued for ~3 h and then set aside overnight. Hot (~60°) aqueous HCl (0.4 *M*; 7.5 ml) was added to it and the mixture stirred for ~1 h before extraction with ethyl acetate. The washed extract was evaporated and the residual paste stirred with HCl (2 *M*) for ~1 h. The solid product that separated was washed with water, dried and crystallised from hot benzene.

For pH measurements the ligand solutions (1×10^{-3} *M*) were prepared in 1,4-dioxane and all the other solutions in double-distilled CO₂-free water. The pH measurements were made on Systronic pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05) after

calibrating with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution at $28 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The following sets of pH-titrations were performed using a standard carbonate-free 0.01 *M* NaOH solution at a fixed ionic strength (0.01 *M* KCl): (i) 6 ml HCl (1×10^{-3} *M*) + 2 ml H₂O + 10 ml dioxane + 2 ml KCl, (ii) 6 ml HCl (1×10^{-3} *M*) + 2 ml H₂O + 9 ml dioxane + 1 ml ligand solution + 2 ml KCl, and (iii) 6 ml HCl (1×10^{-3} *M*) + 1.8 ml H₂O + 9 ml dioxane + 1 ml ligand solution + 2 ml KCl + 0.2 ml metal(II) chloride solution (1×10^{-4} *M*). Duplicate titration was performed in each case under identical conditions.

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